

New combinations in *Melaleuca* (Myrtaceae)

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Abstract: Molecular evidence supports the inclusion of *Beaufortia* R.Br. and *Callistemon* R.Br. within *Melaleuca* L. As a consequence, five species formerly placed in *Beaufortia* and *Callistemon* are transferred to *Melaleuca*. In addition, morphological characters described in the protologue of *Metrosideros lophantha* Vent. support its placement in *Melaleuca*, and a new combination is provided.

Keywords: Australia, *Beaufortia burbidgeae*, *Beaufortia kwongkanicola*, *Beaufortia raggedensis*, *Callistemon forresterae*, *Callistemon purpurascens*, *Metrosideros lophantha*

Introduction

Molecular studies have shown that *Beaufortia* R.Br. and *Callistemon* R.Br. are congeneric with *Melaleuca* L. (Craven et al., 2014). Consequently, *Beaufortia burbidgeae* A.A.Burb., *B. kwongkanicola* A.A.Burb., *B. raggedensis* A.A.Burb., *Callistemon forresterae* Molyneux and *C. purpurascens* S.M.Douglas & S.David are here transferred to *Melaleuca*. In addition, the vegetative and floral characters of *Metrosideros lophantha* Vent., as presented in the protologue, correspond to those of *Melaleuca*, supporting its transfer to that genus.

New combinations

Melaleuca burbidgeae (A.A.Burb.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Beaufortia burbidgeae* A.A.Burb., *Nuytsia* 27: 177. 2016.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, Boolanelling Nature Reserve, Shire of Bruce Rock, 3 October 1997, G.S. Durell 191 (PERTH05209277!).

Distribution: Australia (Western Australia).

Melaleuca forresterae (Molyneux) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Callistemon forresterae* Molyneux, *Muelleria* 8(1): 61. 1993.

Holotype: Australia, Victoria, Upper Genoa River, Gippsland, below the New South Wales border, 37°16'S, 149°22'E, April 1980, *W.M. Molyneux & S.G. Forrester s.n.* (MEL2025155!, Figure 1).

Distribution: Australia (Victoria).

Melaleuca kwongkanicola (A.A.Burb.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Beaufortia kwongkanicola* A.A.Burb., *Nuytsia* 27: 187. 2016.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, East of Chatfield Clarke Road on Green Head Road, 8 October 1997, *B.P. Richardson 0035* (PERTH04948831!).

Distribution: Australia (Western Australia).

Melaleuca lophantha (Vent.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Metrosideros lophantha* Vent., *Descr. Pl. Nouv. pt. 7: t. 69.* 1802. *Callistemon lophanthus* (Vent.) Sweet, *Fl. Australas.* (Sweet) t. 29. 1828.

Lectotype (designated by Callmander et al., 2017): Australia (introduced to the garden of Jacques-Martin Celsin 1792, Montrouge, France), *s.d.*, *É.P. Ventenat s.n.* (G00341539!, Figure 2); isolectotypes G00341540!, G00341541!, W0048413!.

Distribution: Native of Australia. Introduced in China, India, Taiwan and few countries of Africa, Americas and Europe.

Melaleuca purpurascens (S.M.Douglas & S.David) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Callistemon purpurascens* S.M.Douglas & S.David, *Telopea* 18: 266. 2015.

Holotype: Australia, New South Wales, Central Tablelands, unnamed tributary of Megalong Creek north of Nellies Glen Road, eastern Megalong Valley, 15 December 2010, *S.M. Douglas & S. Robyn s.n.* (NSW907108!).

Distribution: Australia (New South Wales).

Melaleuca raggedensis (A.A.Burb.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Beaufortia raggedensis* A.A.Burb., *Nuytsia* 27: 194. 2016.

Holotype: Australia, Western Australia, Mt Ragged, 15 December 1999, *M. Hislop 1956 A* (PERTH05797241!).

Distribution: Australia (Western Australia).

Figure 1: Holotype of *Callistemon forresterae* Molyneux (MEL2025155, © National Herbarium of Victoria, Melbourne, Australia)

Figure 2: Lectotype *Metrosideros lophantha* Vent. (G00341539, © Conservatoire et Jardin botaniques de la Ville de Genève, Switzerland)

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Reference

Craven, L.A., Edwards, R.D. and Cowley, K.J. (2014). New combinations and names in *Melaleuca* (Myrtaceae). *Taxon* 63(3): 663–670. <https://doi.org/10.12705/633.38>